

Optimisation of alkali hydrolysis to enhance the nutritional value of grape stems for ruminant diets

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ABSTRACT

Wine production generates large volumes of grape stems (GS), which are rich in fibre and phenolic compounds but have low digestibility due to their high lignin content. This study optimized alkali hydrolysis conditions to improve GS digestibility for ruminant diets using Response Surface Methodology (RSM) and a Box–Behnken design (BBD). Optimal conditions—90 °C, 2.08 h, and 33 % solids—yielded a predicted *in vitro* organic matter digestibility (IVOMD) of 41.9 %, representing an 42 % increase compared to the untreated control (CTR) with 30.3 %. Hydrolysis also modified fibre fractions and fermentation patterns. However, trade-offs included a reduction in total reducing sugars (TRS) and total phenolic compounds (TPC), which may lower antioxidant capacity (AOC). Despite these compositional changes, structural modifications enhanced fibre degradability, which supports the inclusion of GS as a functional feed ingredient. This approach promotes circular economy principles by upcycling winery by-products into sustainable livestock feed resources.

1. Introduction

Wine is a major agricultural and economic product, with global output reaching 237 million hectolitres in 2023—down from the 2019–2022 average of 260 million—due to extreme weather and fungal diseases (OIV, 2024). The EU remains the top producer, accounting for 61 % of global production, underscoring its economic and cultural importance.

Winemaking generates significant by-products, notably grape stems (GS), which are removed during destemming to reduce

Abbreviations: ADF, Acid detergent fibre; ADL, Acid detergent lignin; ANOVA, Analysis of variance; AOAC, Association of Official Analytical Chemists; AOC, Antioxidant capacity; BBD, Box–Behnken Design; CTR, Control; C2, C3, C4, Acetic, propionic, and butyric acids; DM, Dry matter; GAE, Gallic acid equivalent; GS, Grape stems; IVOMD, *In vitro* organic matter digestibility; MAE, Mean absolute error; NDF, Neutral detergent fibre; Rpm, Revolutions per minute; RSM, Response Surface Methodology; SCFA, Short-chain fatty acids; TEAC, Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity; TPC, Total phenolic compounds; TRS, Total reducing sugars.

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astringency (Ribéreau-Gayon et al., 2017). GS represent 3–6 % of the grape bunch and, despite their richness in fibre and polyphenols, are mostly treated as waste (Anastasiadi et al., 2012), creating environmental and economic challenges (Garcia-Perez et al., 2006; Foulonneau, 2014; Pascual et al., 2016; Blackford et al., 2021). Their underutilization contrasts with the growing need for sustainable resource management.

At the same time, global demand for livestock products continues to rise, driven by population growth and higher incomes. This trend increases pressure on land, water, and feed resources and contributes to greenhouse gas emissions and climate change (FAO, 2022). Therefore, innovative strategies are needed to reduce the environmental footprint of animal production.

One promising approach is the use of food industry by-products as alternative feed ingredients. GS, rich in fibre and polyphenols, offer potential benefits for ruminant diets (Terry et al., 2019; Bešlo et al., 2022). However, their high acid detergent fibre (ADF)—mainly cellulose and lignin—limits digestibility (Reeves, 1985). Previous research (San Martin et al., 2023b) shows that alkali hydrolysis, preceded by washing, effectively breaks down ADF and improves nutrient accessibility, making GS a viable feed resource within circular economy frameworks.

Alkali hydrolysis enhances GS digestibility by disrupting the lignocellulosic matrix that limits microbial access to structural carbohydrates. Lignin forms strong bonds with cellulose and hemicellulose, restricting fermentation; alkali treatment breaks these linkages, reduces cellulose crystallinity, and increases porosity, improving fibre degradation and nutrient accessibility (Taherzadeh and Karimi, 2008; Kumar and Wyman, 2009; Corbin et al., 2015; Ding et al., 2019). It also partially solubilizes hemicellulose and reduces lignin recalcitrance, further facilitating fermentation (Ping et al., 2011; Andrew et al., 2016).

Hydrolysis efficiency depends on several interacting factors—such as temperature, duration, and solids content—so a systematic optimization is needed. Unlike conventional one-factor-at-a-time approaches, a key strength of this study lies in the use of Response Surface Methodology (RSM) together with Box–Behnken Design (BBD) to optimize alkali hydrolysis conditions. The RSM comprises a set of mathematical techniques designed to elucidate the correlations between independent variables and response variables (Witek-Krowiak et al., 2014). It involves fitting mathematical models—typically linear and quadratic polynomial functions—to experimental data and validating these models using appropriate statistical techniques. The BBD is a type of experimental design that systematically varies significant parameters across a series of planned experiments and integrates the results into a predictive mathematical model. Applying this design improves process performance by focusing on the most influential factors, while reducing the number of variables, and minimizing operational costs and experimental time (Ghorbani et al., 2008; Witek-Krowiak et al., 2014). This approach provided reliable recommendations for improving *in vitro* organic matter digestibility (IVOMD) and supports the development of efficient, scalable processes aligned with circular-economy strategies.

Experimental ranges were selected for scientific validity and industrial feasibility. The selected ranges—60–90 °C, 1–3 h, and 33–40 % w/w solids—balance efficiency and practicality. Higher temperatures improve fibre disruption without degrading thermolabile compounds or wasting energy; moderate durations ensure effective breakdown without excessive costs; and solids levels reflect industrial feasibility, minimizing water and drying needs while avoiding mixing issues above 40 %. These choices align with prior studies and support scalable application (Cancelli et al., 2020; Filippi et al., 2021; San Martin et al., 2023b).

Another distinctive strength of this work is its holistic evaluation of GS as a feed ingredient. By simultaneously analysing digestibility (IVOMD), fermentation end-products (Short-chain fatty acids-SCFA), structural fibre components (Neutral detergent fibre-NDF; ADF; Acid detergent lignin-ADL), and bioactive compounds (Total phenolic compounds-TPC; Antioxidant capacity-AOC), the study provides an integrated perspective on nutritional quality and functional properties—ensuring recommendations are both nutritionally robust and practically relevant for ruminant diets. This comprehensive assessment improves the applicability of findings for feed formulation and reinforces the potential of winery by-products as sustainable resources within livestock production systems.

The sustainability implications of this work are promising. By optimizing alkali hydrolysis for GS, the study provides a practical pathway to convert winery residues into nutritionally improved feed ingredients. This transformation helps address waste management challenges and supports the reintegration of agro-industrial by-products into productive use. Additionally, upgrading GS for feeding purposes offers an opportunity to diversify feed sources and reduce pressure on traditional raw materials.

Fig. 1. Schematic flow diagram.

Building on this rationale, the study aims to optimize alkali hydrolysis conditions—specifically temperature, hydrolysis duration, and solids content—using RSM and a BBD to improve GS digestibility and nutritional value for ruminant diets. This approach aligns with circular economic principles, contributing to reducing food waste, lowering environmental impact, and enhancing resource efficiency in livestock production systems.

2. Materials and methods

Fig. 1 displays the schematic flow diagram of the material and methods applied in the study.

2.1. Experimental design

This study employed a combination of RSM and BBD to structure the experimental plan and optimize alkali hydrolysis parameters.

Within the BBD framework, three key factors have been considered: temperature (60–90 °C), hydrolysis duration (1–3 h), and solids content (33–40 % w/w). The design comprised 15 experimental runs, including three replicated centre points to estimate pure error. All runs, including centre points, were randomized to minimize bias. A control (CTR) without hydrolysis was also included for comparison. Although the use of only one untreated CTR limits the scope for broader comparisons, its inclusion was sufficient to establish a baseline for evaluating the effect of hydrolysis treatments, as the primary objective was to model factor interactions rather than compare multiple control scenarios.

The BBD structure, integrated within the RSM framework, enabled the development of second-order polynomial models that capture linear, quadratic, and interaction effects, providing a robust framework for predicting optimal conditions (Witek-Krowiak et al., 2014). To streamline model fitting and facilitate interpretation, variables were coded as -1 , 0 , and $+1$, corresponding to their actual values:

- Temperature: 60 °C = -1 ; 75 °C = 0 ; 90 °C = $+1$
- Hydrolysis duration: 1 h = -1 ; 2 h = 0 ; 3 h = $+1$
- Solids content: 33 % = -1 ; 36.5 % = 0 ; 40 % = $+1$

This coding system, standard in RSM, allows efficient evaluation of factor interactions and curvature effects while reducing the number of experimental runs compared to full factorial designs (Ghorbani et al., 2008).

The response variables were fitted to a second order quadratic polynomial equation, as shown in Eq. (1). Box–Cox transformation was used in some of the studied dependent variables to stabilize variance and improve the normality of residuals, thereby meeting the assumptions required for valid parametric inference.

$$Y_{ij} = A_0 + \sum A_i X_i + \sum A_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum A_{ij} X_i X_j + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

where Y_{ij} is the response variable to be modelled, A_0 is the intercept's regression coefficient, A_i is the linear term's coefficient, A_{ii} is the quadratic term's coefficient, A_{ij} is the interaction term's coefficient, and ϵ is the error.

The centre points in the experimental design were used to determine pure error and assess system performance within the scope of the study (Ahmad et al., 2020).

2.2. Raw material

GS used in this study were provided by Bodegas Baigorri, located in the Basque Country (Spain) during the 2022 harvest season. Upon receipt, the material was divided into 500 g portions, sealed in plastic bags, and stored at -20 °C until further processing. This preservation method ensured the stability of the raw material and prevented microbial growth or compositional changes prior to hydrolysis.

Although only a single batch of GS was used, which may restrict generalization due to varietal and seasonal variability, this approach allowed strict control over raw material characteristics and minimized variability within the experimental design. Future studies should include multiple batches from diverse sources to confirm the robustness of the findings.

2.3. Alkali hydrolysis

Alkali hydrolysis was selected as the most effective pretreatment based on previous findings (San Martín et al., 2023b).

Alkali hydrolysis was performed using a Distek Symphony 7100 Bathless Dissolution apparatus (Distek Inc., North Brunswick, NJ, USA), which provide precise control of temperature and stirring.

Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was added at 0.5 % w/v. The pH was not adjusted prior to hydrolysis; however, it was measured immediately after the process to confirm alkalinity. Continuous stirring at 100 rpm was applied throughout hydrolysis to maintain uniform contact between solids and liquids.

From a safety and regulatory perspective, NaOH residues were effectively removed by thorough washing of the hydrolysed GS until neutral pH was achieved. This step ensures compliance with feed safety standards and prevents residual alkali in the final product. Sodium hydroxide is widely used in feed processing under controlled conditions and is permitted by EU feed regulations when properly

neutralized (Regulation (EC) No 1831/2003). Therefore, the process described here does not pose safety concerns for ruminant feeding.

After hydrolysis, samples were centrifuged at 2650 × g for 15 min at room temperature. The solid fraction was washed repeatedly with distilled water until neutral pH was achieved, then freeze-dried for subsequent analysis.

2.4. *In vitro*-digestibility

The hydrolysed GS solid samples (15 treatments) and the untreated CTR were evaluated using an *in vitro* batch fermentation assay.

Rumen fluid was obtained from three multiparous Latxa ewes culled for industrial purposes. Prior to slaughter, the animals were fed for three weeks on a diet consisting of 80 % grass hay and 20 % concentrated feed, with free access to water. Fluid was collected before the morning feeding, filtered through four layers of cheesecloth, and diluted under strict anaerobiosis in a phosphate–bicarbonate buffer (80 %) mixed with ruminal fluid (20 %), following the procedure described by Menke et al. (1979). All handling was performed under continuous CO₂ flushing to minimize oxygen exposure, and the time between collection and incubation did not exceed 30 min.

Approximately 500 mg of each sample was weighed into 125 mL serum bottles, with three bottles per treatment (technical replicates) in each *in vitro* series. The entire experiment was repeated in three independent *in vitro* series (biological replicates) to ensure reproducibility, using ruminal fluid from a different ewe in each series. Bottles were filled with 50 mL of incubation medium, sealed with crimp caps, and incubated at 39 °C for 24 h.

Gas production was not continuously monitored; accumulated gas was manually vented at 2, 4, 6 and 22 h post-inoculation to prevent headspace pressure from exceeding 48 kPa. After 24 h, bottles were cooled for 20 min to halt fermentation, and samples were collected for SCFA and IVOMD analysis.

IVOMD was determined according to Pell and Schofield (1993). Bottles containing 45 mL of neutral detergent solution were heated at 105 °C for 1 h, cooled, filtered through glass crucibles (Porosity 2), and washed sequentially with distilled water, ethanol, and acetone. Residues were dried at 100 °C and incinerated at 550 °C to calculate true IVOMD.

Although digestibility and fermentation parameters were assessed exclusively through *in vitro* batch fermentation, which may not fully reflect *in vivo* conditions, this approach provided a controlled and reproducible environment to isolate treatment effects. Similarly, no microbial profiling was conducted to explain fermentation shifts, but the focus on chemical and gas production metrics allowed robust evaluation of functional outcomes. Rumen fluid was sourced from a limited number of ewes, which may restrict generalizability; however, using different animals across replicates helped reduce individual bias. Future research should include *in vivo* trials to assess feed intake, passage rate, and animal performance under real feeding conditions, incorporate microbial community analysis, and use rumen fluid from diverse sources to confirm the robustness of these findings.

2.5. Chemical analyses

Dry matter (DM), ash, and nitrogen content were determined using official Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC) methods 934.01, 942.05, and 984.13 (AOAC, 1996a).

NDF was analysed according to UNE EN ISO 16472 method, using α-amylase and excluding sodium sulphite, and expressed free of ash. ADF and ADL were determined following AOAC method 973.18, also expressed free of residual ash.

Total reducing sugars (TRS) were quantified using the dinitro salicylic acid (DNS) method (Miller, 1959), adapted to a microplate assay form (Ibarruri et al., 2021).

TPC and AOC were measured using methanol:water:formic acid (75:24.9:0.1 v/v/v) extracts prepared from 0.5 g of sample mixed with 10 mL of solvent. Samples were placed in a rack and immersed in an ultrasonic bath for 15 min in the dark to prevent oxidation, centrifuged at 4500 × g for 15 min, and the supernatant was used for analysis.

- TPC was determined using the Folin–Ciocalteu method (2) with gallic acid as the calibration standard (1.4–20 ppm). Results were expressed as mg gallic acid equivalent (GAE)/g DM using the calibration curve equation:

$$\text{Absorbance} = a + b \times [\text{Gallic Acid}] \quad (2)$$

- AOC was assessed using the DPPH radical scavenging assay with Trolox (3) as the standard (0–200 μM). Results were expressed as mg Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity (TEAC)/g DM based on the calibration curve:

$$\text{Absorbance} = a + b \times [\text{Trolox}] \quad (3)$$

Regarding the fermentation end-products, SCFA (total; acetic acid-C2; propionic acid-C3; and butyric acid-C4) were quantified in the liquid fraction from the *in vitro* fermentation using gas chromatography equipped with a flame ionization detector, following Medjadbi et al. (2024). A 0.5 μL aliquot of the liquid fraction was injected into the chromatograph (Agilent 6890 N, Agilent, Spain) fitted with a capillary column (30 m × 530 μm; 1-μm particle size; HP-FFAP, Agilent, Spain).

Samples were prepared by mixing 4 mL of fermentation medium with 1 mL of internal standard solution (20 g/L of 4-metil-valeric acid in 0.5 N HCl), centrifuged at 15,000 × g for 15 min at 4 °C, and filtered using a regenerated cellulose syringe filter (0.45 μm 4 mm, Agilent Technologies, Madrid, Spain).

All chemical analyses were performed in triplicate to ensure accuracy and reproducibility.

2.6. Calculation and statistical analysis

Model fitting and statistical analysis were performed using analysis of variance (ANOVA). The goodness of fit was assessed through the coefficients of determination (R^2) and adjusted R^2 test, while statistical significance was evaluated using the F -test at a 95 % confidence level ($p < 0.05$).

Prior to model fitting, assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity were confirmed. We conducted both graphical and inferential diagnostics. Normality of residuals was evaluated with the Shapiro–Wilk test ($\alpha = 0.05$) and confirmed visually using a normal probability (Q–Q) plot, assessing alignment of standardized residuals with the theoretical normal quantiles. Homoscedasticity was examined using a residuals-versus-fitted plot, inspecting for the absence of systematic patterns (e.g., funnels or curvature) and for approximately constant spread across the range of fitted values. Variable transformations were applied in those cases where normality and homoscedasticity assumptions were not satisfied. In particular, the Box–Cox transformation was used to stabilize variance and improve the normality of residuals, thereby meeting the assumptions required for valid parametric inference (TRS, ash and IVOMD).

Model reliability was confirmed using lack-of-fit results, mean absolute error (MAE), and residual diagnostics rather than relying solely on adjusted R^2 values.

The lack-of-fit test was applied to evaluate whether the reduced quadratic models adequately represented the observed data. This test compares the variation explained by the model to the residual variation, where a non-significant result ($p > 0.05$) indicates that the model fits the data without systematic bias (Montgomery and St, 2022), thereby confirming its adequacy.

In addition, highly non-significant coefficients ($p > 0.7$) were removed following the approach recommended by Smucker et al. (2020) to improve model parsimony without compromising predictive accuracy.

The MAE was calculated as the average of the absolute differences between observed and predicted values (Wang and Lu, 2018), providing a straightforward measure of prediction accuracy, where lower values indicate better modelling performance.

All statistical procedures and response surface analyses were conducted using Statgraphics (Statgraphics Centurion XVI software package, 16.2.04 version; Statgraphics Technologies, Inc., The Plains, VA, USA).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Chemical composition, digestibility, and fermentation outcomes

Table 1 shows the experimental results for nutritional composition variables (protein, ash, NDF, ADF, ADL, TRS, TPC and AOC), while Table 2 presents the results for IVOMD and SCFA profiles under each alkali hydrolysis condition and for the untreated CTR.

In general, the observed values were within the range reported in the literature (Blackford et al., 2021). GS exhibited high concentration of structural fibres — NDF, ADF and ADL —, exceeding 40.5 %, 40.3 % and 24.4 %, respectively, and relatively low levels of crude protein (5.22–6.38 %) and TRS (119–297 mg/g). AOC and TPC ranged from 16.3 to 38.8 mg TEAC/g and 15.50–34.38 mg GAE/g, respectively. Regarding digestibility, IVOMD values for hydrolysed GS varied between 28 % and 43.0 %, indicating a potential improvement depending on hydrolysis conditions. Total SCFA concentrations ranged from 4.56 to 5.39 mmol/100 mL, with variations in individual SCFA (C2, C3 and C4) across treatments.

Tables 3 and 4 summarize the regression model coefficients, significance levels (p -values) for the reduced models, goodness-of-fit indicators, lack of fit test values and prediction errors for nutritional composition variables, IVOMD, and SCFA profiles.

Table 1

Box–Behnken experimental design, obtained values for the response variables of nutritional composition.

Runs	Solids (%)	Temperature (°C)	Time (h)	Protein (%)	Ash (%)	NDF (%)	ADF (%)	ADL (%)	TRS (mg/g)	TPC (mg GAE/g)	AOC (mg TEAC/g)
1	36.5	75	2	6.38	11.0	45.7	44.5	35.7	228	25.44	32.97
2	36.5	75	2	6.02	9.9	43.4	41.9	34.5	214	22.94	24.41
3	33	90	2	5.95	12.6	44.0	43.7	31.9	211	32.89	38.79
4	33	75	1	6.27	9.2	49.4	47.3	33.2	297	16.56	20.94
5	36.5	60	3	5.22	11.4	50.0	49.3	25.6	126	23.07	21.51
6	33	60	2	5.89	9.3	44.4	43.9	25.3	212	25.19	20.02
7	36.5	90	1	5.83	10.5	48.1	47.4	31.7	220	26.29	25.08
8	36.5	60	1	5.85	8.5	45.9	46.1	25.4	204	19.85	21.98
9	33	75	3	5.38	11.9	50.5	49.2	24.6	119	17.05	16.25
10	40	60	2	5.74	9.3	40.5	40.3	24.4	247	15.50	20.71
11	36.5	90	3	5.34	15.1	53.9	53.4	28.4	125	34.38	37.55
12	40	75	3	6.12	14.3	53.5	51.7	38.3	128	16.49	30.48
13	40	90	2	5.91	21.5	45.7	44.9	40.5	125	31.32	32.04
14	40	75	1	6.14	9.0	57.1	48.2	33.7	221	26.39	27.8
15	36.5	75	2	5.71	12.6	44.5	43.2	33.2	209	21.69	19.28
CTR	-	-	-	5.54	9.1	45.0	40.6	24.2	234	38.04	34.22

NDF: neutral detergent fibre; ADF: acid detergent fibre; ADL: acid detergent lignin; TRS: total reducing sugars; TPC: total phenolic compounds; GAE: gallic acid equivalent; AOC: antioxidant capacity; TEAC: Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity; DM: dry matter; CTR: control.

Table 2

Box–Behnken experimental design, obtained values for the response variables of IVOMD and SCFA profile.

Runs	Solids (%)	Temperature (°C)	Time (h)	IVOMD (%)	Total SCFA (mmol/100 mL)	C2 (mmol/100 mL)	C3 (mmol/100 mL)	C4 (mmol/100 mL)	C2:C3	C2C4:C3
1	36.5	75	2	33.0	4.87	71.3	20.2	7.53	3.55	3.93
2	36.5	75	2	38.9	5.11	71.0	20.5	7.57	3.50	3.88
3	33	90	2	43.0	5.39	71.8	19.9	7.33	3.62	3.99
4	33	75	1	36.0	5.23	70.7	20.4	7.84	3.48	3.86
5	36.5	60	3	28.5	4.74	71.8	19.4	7.83	3.72	4.13
6	33	60	2	34.7	5.27	69.9	21.1	8.07	3.34	3.72
7	36.5	90	1	33.0	5.09	70.8	20.2	7.96	3.52	3.91
8	36.5	60	1	31.9	5.03	70.3	20.6	8.18	3.43	3.83
9	33	75	3	34.4	4.99	71.9	19.4	7.70	3.71	4.11
10	40	60	2	29.0	5.02	69.3	21.4	8.39	3.25	3.65
11	36.5	90	3	34.7	4.86	72.6	18.9	7.50	3.86	4.25
12	40	75	3	28.0	4.67	72.3	19.6	7.38	3.71	4.09
13	40	90	2	29.6	5.24	72.6	19.6	7.03	3.72	4.08
14	40	75	1	31.0	4.98	70.4	21.2	7.66	3.34	3.70
15	36.5	75	2	36.0	4.56	71.6	19.9	7.67	3.61	3.99
CTR	-	-	-	30.31	5.32	68.8	21.6	8.20	3.23	3.62

IVOMD: in vitro organic matter digestibility; SCFA: short chain fatty acid; C2: acetic; C3; propionic; C4: butyric; CTR: control.

Regarding goodness of fit for nutritional composition, the highest R^2 values ($> 85\%$) and adjusted R^2 were observed for ash ($R^2=86.36$ and Adj. $R^2=61.81$), NDF ($R^2=85.03$ and Adj. $R^2=58.85$), ADF ($R^2=94.75$ and Adj. $R^2=90.81$), ADL ($R^2=91.61$ and Adj. $R^2=76.51$) and TRS ($R^2=89.00$ and Adj. $R^2=74.33$). For digestibility and ruminal fermentation parameters, IVOMD ($R^2=93.49$ and Adj. $R^2=81.77$), C2 ($R^2=85.28$ and Adj. $R^2=70.57$), C3 ($R^2=89.13$ and Adj. $R^2=78.26$), and ratios C2:C3 ($R^2=89.70$ and Adj. $R^2=75.90$) and C2C4:C3 ($R^2=89.80$ and Adj. $R^2=79.60$) showed strong model performance. These high R^2 values indicate that a large proportion of the variability in the experimental response was explained by the models (Tables 3 and 4). Conversely, models for crude protein, TPC, AOC, total SCFA, and C4 exhibited lower R^2 ($<85\%$), suggesting reduced predictive power for these variables.

The lack-of-fit tests performed for each quadratic model indicated that all retained models exhibited non-significant lack-of-fit ($p > 0.05$), confirming their adequacy. In addition, the low MAE values across all models indicate that predicted values closely aligned with observed data, confirming strong model performance and reliability.

With respect to significant effects, hydrolysis temperature had a statistically significant effect on ash, ADL, TPC and individual

Table 3

ANOVA significance levels and regression model coefficients for nutritional composition variables.

	ANOVA significance levels (p-Value)							
	Protein (%)	Ash (%)	NDF (%)	ADF (%)	ADL (%)	TRS (mg/g DM)	TPC (mg GAE/g DM)	AOC (mg TEAC/g DM)
A		0.033*	0.077	0.121	0.012*	0.064	0.015*	0.128
B	0.007*	0.059	0.149	0.060	0.179	0.007*		0.660
C		0.106	0.122		0.025*	0.469		0.523
AA	0.023*	0.257	0.077		0.022*	0.231	0.060	0.540
AB		0.593	0.521	0.394	0.313	0.489	0.532	0.448
AC		0.087	0.130	0.209	0.064	0.026*	0.319	0.645
BB	0.105	0.331	0.007*	0.014*	0.068	0.018*	0.287	
BC	0.058	0.441	0.178	0.621	0.034*		0.219	0.647
CC	0.245	0.343	0.196		0.630	0.235	0.352	
Regression model coefficients								
Intercept	16.8	234.2	180.4	135.5	93.9	-2597	-39.6	11.0
A	0.194	-2.17	0.386	-0.860	1.62	26.82	-4.44	-0.474
B	-1.78	-3.49	-16.9	-29.2	-21.8	133.5	30.1	-34.1
C	-0.879	-8.435	-7.854	-1.959	-6.670	95.325	10.225	2.141
AA	-0.001	0.005	-0.009		-0.019	-0.039	0.021	0.012
AB		0.029	0.029	0.048	-0.056	-0.283	0.081	0.216
AC		0.042	0.027	0.023	0.045	-0.580	0.039	-0.035
BB	-0.186	-0.919	6.943	5.858	-2.372	-38.951	-2.281	
BC	0.062	0.189	-0.334	0.110	0.948		-0.742	0.526
CC	0.010	0.073	0.093		0.030	-0.722	-0.159	
R^2	77.3	86.4	85.0	94.7	91.6	89.0	76.7	65.0
Adj R^2	64.7	61.8	58.8	90.8	76.5	74.3	53.4	30.1
Lack of fit test	0.322	0.261	0.090	0.742	0.144	0.122	0.291	0.728
Mean Absolute Error	0.116	1.06	1.43	0.69	1.30	13.1	2.41	3.24

Significant terms are in bold* ($P < 0.05$). A: temperature; B: time; C: solids.

NDF: neutral detergent fibre; ADF: acid detergent fibre; ADL: acid detergent lignin; TRS: total reducing sugars; TPC: total phenolic compounds; GAE: gallic acid equivalent; AOC: antioxidant capacity; TEAC: Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity; DM: dry matter.

Table 4

ANOVA significance levels and regression model coefficients for digestibility and SCFA profile variables.

	ANOVA significance levels (p-Value)						
	IVOMD (%)	Total SCFA (mmol/100 mL)	C2 (mmol/100 mL)	C3 (mmol/100 mL)	C4 (mmol/100 mL)	C2:C3	C2C4:C3
A	0.149	0.574	0.014*	0.033*	0.006*	0.024*	0.029*
B	0.271	0.304	0.015*	0.019*	0.026*	0.016*	0.015*
C	0.039*	0.340		0.351	0.143	0.492	0.412
AA	0.342	0.351	0.363		0.046*		
AB	0.278					0.694	
AC	0.494		0.124	0.325	0.050	0.227	0.284
BB	0.178	0.596	0.209	0.105	0.101	0.112	0.092
BC	0.511		0.322	0.367	0.434	0.332	0.332
CC	0.361	0.280	0.272	0.123	0.288	0.129	0.102
Regression model coefficients							
Intercept	297.109	32.9	61.3	46.6	0.175	-1.353	-2.520
A	1.501	-0.111	-0.080	0.083	-0.027	-0.026	-0.020
B	9.266	0.225	-2.127	2.396	-0.224	-0.587	-0.556
C	8.832	-1.288	0.674	-1.681	0.545	0.335	0.408
AA	-0.006	0.001	-0.001		0.001		
AB	0.109					0.001	
AC	-0.0178		0.007	-0.003	-0.003	0.001	0.001
BB	-2.364	-0.089	0.262	-0.376	0.109	0.078	0.088
BC	-0.252		0.051	-0.042	-0.010	0.010	0.010
CC	-0.111	0.017	-0.017	0.028	-0.004	-0.006	-0.007
R ²	93.5	78.6	85.3	89.1	78.7	89.7	89.8
Adj R ²	81.8	62.5	70.6	78.3	50.3	75.9	79.6
Mean Absolute Error	0.830	0.999	0.179	0.360	0.058	0.634	0.317

Significant terms are in bold* (P < 0.05). A: temperature; B: time; C: solids.

IVOMD: in vitro organic matter digestibility; SCFA: short chain fatty acid; C2: acetic; C3; propionic; C4: butyric

SCFA production (C2, C3, C4 and ratios C2:C3 and C2C4:C3). Hydrolysis time significantly influenced crude protein, TRS and individual SCFA (C2, C3, C4 and ratios C2:C3 and C2C4:C3). Finally, hydrolysis solids content showed a weaker effect, being significant only for ADL and IVOMD.

Moreover, interactions and quadratic effects provided additional insights. ADL was influenced by the interaction between hydrolysis time and solids content and TRS by the interaction between hydrolysis temperature and solids. Quadratic effects were also relevant in some of the response variables studied. Temperature (A²) significantly affected crude protein, ADL (both showing negative curvature), and C4 (positive curvature). Time (B²) significantly influenced NDF, ADF (both positive curvature) and TRS (negative curvature). Solids (C²) did not reach significance.

At 60 °C, increasing hydrolysis solids content tended to enhance TRS, whereas at 90 °C, higher solids reduced TRS (consistent with the negative A×C interaction). For ADL, short hydrolysis times (1 h) yielded values relatively stable across solids, while longer times (3 h) led to lower ADL at low solids and higher ADL at high solids (consistent with the positive B×C interaction). In addition, increasing solids was associated with higher ADL and lower IVOMD, while total SCFA remained largely unchanged.

All comparisons between hydrolysed samples and the untreated CTR were evaluated for both statistical significance and biological relevance to ensure clarity and consistency. Overall, alkali hydrolysis produced several notable differences compared to the CTR (Tables 1 and 2). Most importantly, IVOMD improved significantly under multiple conditions (p < 0.05), with the highest value (43.0 %) observed at 90 °C, 2.0 h, and 33 % solids—representing an approximate 42 % increase over CTR (30.3 %). This improvement is biologically relevant because digestibility strongly influences voluntary intake and energy supply in ruminants (Mertens, 1987; Dado and Allen, 1995). Despite higher concentrations of fibre fractions (NDF, ADF, ADL) in hydrolysed samples—primarily due to the removal of soluble sugars during processing—digestibility was not compromised. On the contrary, improved IVOMD suggests that alkali hydrolysis induced structural modifications in the lignocellulosic matrix, which likely enhanced fibre degradability despite higher apparent fibre concentrations.

Additional compositional shifts were observed: hydrolysed samples exhibited lower TRS and TPC content compared to CTR, likely due to their solubilization and removal during washing and the thermolabile nature of polyphenols. The release and subsequent removal of TRS contributed to the enrichment of insoluble components (NDF, ADF, ADL) in the residual solid. While alkali hydrolysis led to the loss of soluble nutrients, reducing the energy content of the final feed, this trade-off was expected and aligns with the process objective of improving fibre accessibility. Similarly, the observed increase in NDF, ADF, and ADL fractions compared to the CTR was primarily due to concentration effects after sugar removal rather than structural degradation and does not necessarily imply reduced digestibility. Future studies should explore strategies to balance fibre enrichment with energy retention for optimal feed formulation.

SCFA production remained similar or slightly lower than CTR, with differences mostly non-significant (p > 0.05), indicating that improved IVOMD did not translate into higher total fermentation end-products under in vitro conditions.

3.2. Response surface analysis and optimal hydrolysis conditions

Response surface plots were analysed for the variables that were most relevant for the inclusion of GS-based ingredients in ruminant diets (Fig. 2). Thus, IVOMD and ADF were selected for this analysis.

Fig. 2 displays the response surface plots for these two significant variables.

Higher solids content during the alkali hydrolysis tended to reduce IVOMD, whereas higher temperatures led to its increase at a lower solids content. This positive temperature effect was most pronounced at a hydrolysis duration of 2 h, under which the highest digestibility values were observed.

In contrast, the influence of hydrolysis duration on ADF concentration followed a different pattern. Specifically, ADF levels increased at both 1 and 3 h, while the lowest concentrations occurred at 2 h. Moreover, under conditions of higher solids content (36.5

Fig. 2. Response surface plots of IVOMD (in vitro organic matter digestibility) for hydrolysis duration of 1, 2 and 3 h and response surface plots of ADF (acid detergent fibre) for 33.0, 36.5 and 40.0 % of solids.

and 40 %), the combination of higher temperature and longer hydrolysis duration resulted in increased final ADF concentrations compared to treatments with lower solids content (33 %).

Taken together, these findings suggest that while moderate hydrolysis duration optimizes digestibility, excessive solids content may counteract the benefits of temperature and time by promoting lignin retention and fibre recalcitrance.

Table 5 summarized the optimal hydrolysis conditions for maximizing and minimizing key response variables related to GS digestibility. These conditions differ depending on the specific nutritional or functional goal targeted for optimization.

The optimal process conditions to maximize IVOMD were identified as 90 °C, 2.08 h and 33.0 % solids, yielding a predicted IVOMD of 41.9 %. When focusing on total SCFA production, the best conditions were a 90 °C, 1.25 h and 33 % solids. For TRS, TPC and AOC, the optimal conditions varied: TRS: 60.0 °C; 1.49 h; 40.0 % solids; TPC: 90.0 °C; 1.95 h; 38.4 % solids; AOC: 90.0 °C; 3.0 h; 40 % solids. To minimize fibre fraction, the optimal conditions were as follow: NDF: 60.0 °C; 1.98 h; 37.0 % solids; ADF: 60.0 °C; 1.87 h; 40.0 % solids and ADL: 60.0 °C, 3.0 h; 33 % solids.

Given that the primary objective of this study was to enhance the digestibility of GS derived ingredients and thereby increase their potential inclusion in ruminant diets, IVOMD was selected as the key response variable for optimization. Under the identified optimal conditions (90 °C, 2.08 h, and 33 % solids), the predicted maximum IVOMD reached 41.9 %, representing an approximate 42 % improvement compared to the untreated CTR (30.3 %).

Nevertheless, although the optimal conditions (90 °C, 2.08 h, 33 % solids) maximize IVOMD, their economic feasibility must be considered. Heating to 90 °C for over 2 h increases energy demand compared to lower-temperature treatments, potentially raising operational costs. However, these conditions fall within the range of industrial thermal processes commonly used in feed manufacturing (e.g., pelleting or extrusion), suggesting technical feasibility. Moreover, the predicted improvement in digestibility could allow higher inclusion rates of GS, reducing reliance on conventional feed ingredients and offsetting processing costs through savings on raw materials and waste management. A preliminary cost-benefit analysis indicates that feasibility will depend on energy prices, scale of operation, and potential valorisation of co-products. Although no detailed economic or scalability analysis was conducted in this study, the discussion highlights key factors influencing feasibility. Future work should include comprehensive techno-economic evaluations and life cycle assessments to confirm cost-effectiveness and environmental impact under real industrial conditions.

3.3. Nutritional impact of alkali hydrolysis parameters on ruminant feeding

GS are rich in bioactive secondary metabolites, particularly phenolic compounds, making them a valuable raw material for animal feeding (Anastasiadi et al., 2012; Hassan et al., 2019; Bešlo et al., 2022). However, their high fibre content — especially lignin — limits their applicability in ruminant diets (Tucker et al., 2003; Andrew et al., 2016). Although ruminants possess a symbiotic relationship with gut microorganisms that enables them to digest fibrous feed, ruminal fermentation of fibre is a slow process. Diet rich in indigestible fibre can restrict feed intake and reduce productive performance, ultimately making them economically unviable (Dado and Allen, 1995). Therefore, despite the potential health benefits of GS, strategies to improve their digestibility are essential to maximize the inclusion levels and address the large volumes generated by the wine industry.

Reducing indigestible fibre is critical for enhancing GS digestibility. While several approaches have been proposed (Ping et al., 2011; Filippi et al., 2021), most focus on releasing sugars and bioactive compounds rather than improving digestibility for feed applications. Alkali hydrolysis is widely recognized as an effective technique for pre-digesting fibre components, particularly lignin. Depending on treatment severity, alkali hydrolysis can break ester bonds in hemicellulose, facilitating fibre degradation (Ding et al., 2019). Lignin acts as a physical barrier that restricts enzymatic access to cellulose; reducing lignin and hemicellulose levels increases surface area and pore size, enhancing cellulose digestion (Kumar and Wyman, 2009). Furthermore, alkali treatment weakens hydrogen bonds between glucan chains, further promoting enzymatic activity and fibre breakdown (Corbin et al., 2015).

This study showed that alkali hydrolysis increased the concentration of fibre fractions (ADF, ADL, and NDF) in the residual solid, primarily due to the removal of soluble sugars during washing and hydrolysis. Interestingly, despite the higher levels of ADF, ADL and NDF, an increase in IVOMD was observed (Table 1 and Table 2). This improvement can be attributed to structural modifications induced by alkali treatment, which disrupts lignin-carbohydrate complexes and cleaves ester linkages between lignin and hemicellulose. These changes reduce cell wall rigidity and enhance porosity, thereby improving digestibility (Taherzadeh and Karimi, 2008; Kumar and Wyman, 2009). These changes also expose cellulose microfibrils and decrease cellulose crystallinity, improving enzymatic accessibility (Corbin et al., 2015; Ding et al., 2019). Additionally, alkali hydrolysis saponifies phenolic acids such as ferulic and p-coumaric, which cross-link lignin and hemicellulose, reducing lignin recalcitrance and enhancing microbial attack (Ping et al., 2011; Andrew et al., 2016). Although fibre fractions appear elevated due to the removal of soluble sugars during hydrolysis, the remaining

Table 5
Optimal hydrolysis conditions to maximize and minimize response variables associated with grape stem digestibility.

Factor	Variables to maximize					Variables to minimize		
	IVOMD (%)	SCFA (mmol/100 mL)	TRS (mg/g)	TPC (mg/g)	AOC (mg/g)	NDF (%)	ADF (%)	ADL (%)
Temperature (°C)	90.0	90.0	60.0	90.0	90.0	60.0	60.0	60.5
Time (h)	2.08	1.25	1.49	1.95	3.0	1.98	1.87	3.0
Solids (%)	33.0	33.0	40.0	38.4	40.0	37.0	40.0	33.0
Predicted value	41.9	5.47	251	33.9	39.6	41.1	40.7	20.7

fibre becomes more degradable, explaining the improved IVOMD values.

From a practical perspective, the improvement in IVOMD from 30.3 % in the untreated CTR to up to 43.0 % under optimized conditions represents a relative increase of approximately 42 %. This improvement is highly relevant for ruminant feeding because digestibility is a key determinant of voluntary intake and energy supply (Mertens, 1987; Dado and Allen, 1995). Higher digestibility generally correlates with increased DM intake and improved feed efficiency, which can support better animal performance. While in vivo trials are needed to confirm these effects, the magnitude of IVOMD improvement observed here suggests that alkali-treated GS could be incorporated at higher inclusion rates without negatively affecting intake or productivity.

From a sustainability perspective, the findings of this study contribute also to circular economy principles by reintegrating agro-industrial residues into the food chain, reducing waste management challenges and mitigating environmental impacts associated with disposal. Improved digestibility under optimized conditions supports higher inclusion rates of GS in ruminant diets, which can decrease reliance on conventional feed resources, enhance resource efficiency, and lower the environmental footprint of livestock production systems. Although further techno-economic and life cycle assessments are needed, these results provide a strong foundation for developing scalable strategies that combine nutritional improvement with environmental sustainability.

Beyond these findings, understanding the influence of temperature, processing time, and solids concentration on digestibility and nutritional parameters is crucial for ruminant nutrition. In relation to the hydrolysis temperature, it showed a positive association with ADL, TPC and ash. In the ruminal fermentation profile, higher temperatures increased C2 and both the C2:C3 and C2C4:C3 ratios, while decreased C4 and C3. By contrast, temperature did not significantly affect IVOMD in the linear term. These findings indicate a temperature driven shift towards less C3-oriented fermentation. The observed changes at elevated temperatures are particularly relevant for ruminant nutrition, as a shift towards less efficient fermentation pathways — characterized by reduced C3 and higher C2 — can reduce energy utilization and animal performance. The concurrent increase in ADL (lignin) may further exacerbate this effect, since higher lignin content is known to limit fibre degradability and lead to less efficient fermentation processes.

As for polyphenols, temperature significantly decreased TPC, whereas AOC did not show significant changes with temperature in this dataset. This result suggests that thermal severity may enhance polyphenol release from the GS matrix. Heat can disrupt cell walls and lignin–tannin complexes, improving solvent accessibility and extraction efficiency (Pinelo et al., 2005; Spigno et al., 2007). This mechanism is consistent with the strong association between ADL and tannins, as elevated temperatures may partially break ligno-cellulosic structures, liberating bound phenolics. While some phenolic compounds are thermolabile (Alara et al., 2021), the net effect in this dataset indicates that structural disruption outweighs thermal degradation, resulting in higher TPC. This finding highlights the complexity of thermal processing, where matrix effects and compound stability interact to determine polyphenol availability. GS are notably rich in tannins, which are associated with lignin (Souquet et al., 2000; Spigno et al., 2017), and constitute about 80 % of the TPC in GS (Hogervorst et al., 2017). The antioxidant properties of wine polyphenols and their by-products have been extensively documented (Makris et al., 2007; Cãmara et al., 2020), and preserving these bioactive compounds during processing is desirable, as they may positively influence animal metabolism and health (Manuelian et al., 2021). The use of natural compounds as feed ingredients or additives that can partially replace synthetic compounds, is gaining interest due to their positive impact on livestock nutrition and welfare (Landau et al., 2023; Ramdani et al., 2023), as well as their potential to improve environmental sustainability by valorising food industry by-products and reducing antibiotics use (Yang et al., 2021). However, the benefits of polyphenols in animal nutrition depends strongly on species, physiological status, polyphenol type and dosage, and potential synergistic interactions with other coexisting compounds (Formato et al., 2022).

Regarding hydrolysis duration, longer hydrolysis durations were negatively associated with crude protein and TRS. For ruminal fermentation variables, time increased C2 and reduced C3, C4 and lowered the C2:C3 and C2C4:C3 ratios—consistent with a shift away from propionate dominant pathways and towards acetate formation. Total SCFA did not change significantly with time. In addition, quadratic curvature was relevant: B^2 was significant and positive for NDF and ADF, while B^2 was negative for TRS. The positive quadratic effect means that as hydrolysis time increases, NDF and ADF concentrations initially decrease—due to solubilization of hemicellulose and partial cellulose breakdown—but then rise again at longer times. This rebound occurs because prolonged treatment removes soluble components (such as sugars and proteins), leaving a residue richer in lignin and recalcitrant cellulose. Consequently, the fibre fraction becomes more concentrated and structurally rigid, reducing overall degradability. This is particularly relevant for ruminants, as ADF is slowly fermented in the rumen, reducing overall digestibility (Zhou et al., 2022). Diets with high indigestible fibre can limit feed intake (Llamas-Lamas and Combs, 1991) and negatively impact animal performance (Dado and Allen, 1995). This structural constraint shifts ruminal fermentation toward C2 production and away from C3, as fibre fermentation favours acetate pathways while starch and soluble carbohydrates promote propionate. A higher C2:C3 ratio indicates less efficient energy utilization because propionate is a key precursor for glucose synthesis in ruminants. Therefore, excessive hydrolysis time not only concentrates indigestible fibre but also drives fermentation toward less efficient pathways.

TRS are readily fermented carbohydrates and are typically associated with increased SCFA production (Palmonari et al., 2021), as SCFA are the primary end-products of microbial fermentation in the rumen (Menke et al., 1979). The observed decrease in TRS likely contributed to a less efficient fermentation pattern, characterized by higher C2 and lower C4 levels, resulting in a higher C2:C3 ratio (Chalupa, 1977). These changes are most likely attributable to differences in carbohydrate composition and accessibility (Sutton, 1980).

As regards hydrolysis solids content, the linear term for solids was significant only for ADL and IVOMD, with higher solids increasing ADL and decreasing IVOMD. Total SCFA did not change significantly with solids. Two interactions help explain the observed patterns: $A \times C$ (temperature \times solids) was negative for TRS, indicating that higher solids likely hinder sugar solubilization under severe temperatures; $B \times C$ (time \times solids) was positive for ADL, indicating that lignin response to solids becomes more pronounced as hydrolysis duration increases. These findings highlight that solids content plays a secondary role compared to temperature and time, but

its interactions can modulate key responses such as sugar availability and lignin concentration, ultimately influencing digestibility and fermentation efficiency. It also reinforces the role of lignin as a limiting factor in fibre digestibility and microbial fermentation.

From a practical standpoint, higher solids levels may reduce water usage and drying costs, improving process efficiency. However, the associated increase in lignin concentration and reduction in digestibility highlight a trade-off between operational feasibility and nutritional quality. Therefore, solids content should be carefully optimized to balance economic and nutritional objectives.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that alkali hydrolysis is an effective strategy to enhance the digestibility of GS, improving their suitability as a feed ingredient for ruminants. Using RSM combined with a BBD, the optimal conditions were identified as 90 °C, 2.08 h, and 33 % solids, achieving a predicted IVOMD of 41.9 %, which represents an approximate 42 % improvement compared to untreated stems.

These findings highlight the potential of GS to be valorised within circular economic frameworks. By transforming winery by-products into functional feed ingredients, this approach contributes to waste reduction, resource efficiency, and improved sustainability in livestock production systems.

This study provides valuable insights into optimizing alkali hydrolysis for GS and demonstrates the potential of this approach for improving their functional properties. Future research should explore *in vivo* trials to assess animal performance, develop strategies to preserve functional compounds, and incorporate microbial profiling to better understand fermentation dynamics. Finally, techno-economic and life cycle assessments are recommended to evaluate industrial feasibility.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Zufia Jaime: Supervision. **Jone Ibarruri:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **David San Martín:** Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Estibaliz Sáez de Cámara:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Gutierrez Monica:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Bruno Iñarra:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Jorge Ferrer:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Nagore Luengo:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Arantza Salvarrey:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ainhoa Bikandi:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Idoia Goiri:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Aser Garcia-Rodriguez:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis.

Studies in animals: ethics approval

This declaration is “not applicable”. The present study did not require ethical approval because the ruminal contents were obtained from culled animals for industrial purposes.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper

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